

Active Learning and New Technologies: Towards Better Learning

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Abstract

Digitalisation has revolutionised the way many areas of our societies work, but until recently only impacted university education to a limited extent. However, after the pandemic it has become clear for decision makers, professors, and students that the technology has a lot to offer, and that digital technologies can support teaching and learning activities in many ways, from improved collaboration tools, to the possibility of online meetings/classes, via interactive tools that can be used in the classroom and all the way to data-driven approaches for predicting students failing exams or dropping out of their studies. With this paper, we aim to support both professors and decision makers in navigating the plethora of digital tools, keeping in mind that the main purpose is to create meaningful and challenging learning experiences for the students – rather than trying out new technology for the sake of technology. We first present a taxonomy for different types of tools, to differentiate between e.g. administrative tools, collaboration tools, communication tools, databases, hardware, artificial intelligence, virtual/augmented reality, streaming tools, tools for interactive teaching, and learning management systems. Following this, we discuss how the different categories of tools can be used to enhance our teaching-learning environments with particular focus on creation of active learning experiences, didactical considerations, and on the impact of professor and student roles. Many of the technologies enable the students to work and learn together with their peers, which is positive, but it also changes the role of the professor in the direction of being more of a facilitator, a guide. Moreover, the technologies also support the creation of problem-based learning situations not only because students get access to learning resources when they need them but also because the new technologies support collaboration across organisational and geographical boundaries. The new tools can also be used to simulate realistic environments and experiments that were not possible before and will help universities to cope with new reality supported by digitalisation.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Learning Technologies; Problem Based Learning.

1 Introduction

This study is motivated by a recent reflection on the use of technology in universities across Latin America, which indicates the use remains low even after the Covid-19 pandemic (Metared TIC, 2023). Technology has a lot to offer to facilitate the learning process and faculty needs help navigating the current landscape (Morales-Urrutia et al., n.d.). Unfortunately, faculty are often on their own when it comes to the use of technology for teaching and learning, and it is not uncommon to see each faculty member starting from scratch with their own set of tools including both getting familiar with the technicalities, as well as trying to fit it into relevant didactical contexts. While this approach appeals to some, it does not provide for a wider uptake of technologies and the advantages its use can provide. With this paper, we hope to make it easier for a broader group of faculty to embrace new technologies and use them in ways that make sense also didactically.

The main contribution of the paper is that it provides a useful overview for faculty, who would like to improve teaching and learning through the use of new technologies. This is achieved by first proposing a taxonomy to classify tools according to their use, considering an active learning environment, followed by examples of how the different categories of tools can be used to enhance teaching and learning environments. Then the change

in roles of both professors and students is addressed, before closing the paper with discussions and conclusions.

2 Taxonomy

Based on the proposed classification of technological resources presented by María & Cacheiro (2011), in which the resources are classified as resources for information, resources for collaboration and resources for learning, and also on the proposed functions that tools could have, we propose a taxonomy that can help faculty to navigate the landscape of technologies and also to reflect on its use. We also consider the fact that Covid-19 did expose us to a myriad of technologies that complement the previous classification and left us with an ample set of options which are hard to navigate. We propose seven dimensions for our taxonomy which we will refer to as ACTIVE:

A = Activation or engagement. This dimension describes tools used to activate metacognition and engage students. This can be both inside and outside of the classroom. It can include gamification and digital boards, where students are contributing, but it can also be tools that facilitate discussions between students. It also includes tools used for reflection.

C = Communication. This dimension includes all tools that facilitate information sharing and the creation and use of learning resources to provide meaningful communication among team members.

T = Teamwork. This dimension includes all tools that facilitate the joint construction of knowledge as well as discussion or consensus when needed. Teaming might be disciplinary or interdisciplinary.

I = Interactivity. This dimension includes all tools that facilitate simulation, observation, exploration and experimentation between two or more people or generative AI tools.

V = Virtualisation. This dimension includes all tools that allow students and professors to interact in a space that is different from the physical classroom.

E = Evaluation. This dimension includes all tools that facilitate formative or summative, graded or non-graded, individual or group, self or peer, feedback or assessment before, during or after classes.

Working with the taxonomy leads to many reflections and discussions among the authors, which are important to keep in mind when reading through the dimensions. We observe a trend, where different classes of the taxonomy are merging into tool suites, which cover multiple (or all) aspects of learning and/or project work - one early example being the ILICE platform, which attempts to support all stages of projects in the context of Problem Based Learning (Sørensen & Pedersen, 2018). At the same time, there is also a movement towards integration of standalone tools. One example of many is the integration between Github and Slack.

3 Enhancing Teaching and Learning environments through technology

Enhancing teaching and learning environments (TLE) is a continuous challenge for professors. When professors were asked about their reasons to implement changes in their courses or changes in their teaching practices, it was found that there are three main drivers: First, the coherence between the courses and the educational purposes of the program. In other words, the alignment between the course objectives and the competencies of the program has gained importance not only because of the accreditation system in place but also as a result of understanding the importance of instructional alignment. Second, the response to claims identified by students as part of the need for developing courses that are meaningful along their majors and courses that will prepare them to solve real-world problems. Third, professors expressed a genuine interest in innovating

and implementing what they have learned during pedagogical training (Fernandez Rodriguez & Gutierrez Iglesias, 2021).

Despite the reasons behind its implementation, when professors decide to integrate technological tools in their teaching and learning environments, they should reflect on the following: what is the **purpose** of using this tool or technology in my course? *How does this tool or technology contribute to the student's achievement of the course and program objectives?* And more importantly, *do students understand the contribution and value of these tools in their learning process?* This reflection will cause professors to avoid the use of tools or technologies for the sake of technology and rethink professors and students' role relative to those tools and technologies.

Considering the ACTIVE taxonomy, examples of how the technology can enhance the TLE are presented for each dimension in Table 1.

Table 1. Examples of teaching and learning enhancements in class based on technology used.

Taxon	Examples of Technology/Tools	Examples of Enhancement of the TLE
A	Search and Information Publishing Tools (Google, Bing). Chatbots (ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini, Claude, Mistral). Academic databases (Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct).	Asking students to compare information from chatGPT relative to their previous knowledge. Asking students to identify their knowledge gaps and navigate DB and search engines to have a new understanding.
C	Video conference tools (Zoom, Teams, Meet). Instant messaging tools (Slack, Discord, WhatsApp). Learning Management Systems (Moodle, Canva, Bridge Space).	Creating interdisciplinary or multicultural teams to solve problems. Facilitating blended environments (physical and virtual). Organize communication within smaller and larger teams in a structured way. Support community building, by providing a virtual communication space less formal than e.g. emails, but more organised than just chats.
T	Digital boards (Miro, Mural, Jamboard) LaTeX editor Tool (Overleaf). Platforms for version control (Github). Prototype generation tools (Figma). Cloud-based text processing tools (Google docs). Graphic design creation tools (Canva, Geneally).	Creating interdisciplinary or multicultural teams to solve problems. Using MIRO templates facilitates the co-construction of ideas or solutions for a problem. Information is accessible any time and can be modified in real-time. Shared documents with e.g. space for comments and discussions make it possible to construct knowledge together both synchronous and asynchronous.
I	Digital boards (Padlet, Jamboard). Real-time response systems (Mentimeter, Socrative, Kahoot).	Anonymously, ask students to identify their knowledge gaps or teamwork weaknesses during a project. Anonymity will encourage students to participate freely and honestly. It facilitates building upon questions and inputs from other students.
V	Virtual, augmented, and mixed reality tools (Spatial, Meta spark). Video streaming services (YouTube). Podcast tools (Podomatic). Learning Management System (Google Classroom). Digital boards (Open board). Virtual hackerlabs (Haaukins).	Allowing students to decide which deliverable format would be better. This will enhance their autonomy in decision making and argument skills as well as their creativity. Makes it possible to use visual content, sometimes in active formats such as with "virtual laboratories".
E	Real-time response systems (Mentimeter, Socrative, Kahoot, Quizizz, Google forms). Tools for creating rubrics (RubiStar).	Use these tools when needing to tune the class, providing instant feedback or allowing students to self-evaluate their experience of level of understanding achieved.

While the table provides a list of non-exhaustive examples, we believe it demonstrates an approach of how explicitly formulated goals for improving the TLE can motivate the introduction of relevant tools to support these goals. In our experience, having clear goals - which are communicated to both students and other faculty members involved in a given course or learning experience - is a crucial part of achieving the goals.

In the next section, we address how the use of different technologies change the roles of both professors and students in the learning situation.

4 Professor's and Student's roles in TLE supported by technology

The role of professors and students has been in continuous evolution since every discipline and every pedagogical framework requires an adjustment in each one of the roles. For instance, moving towards flipped classrooms required to change from the professor-centred to the student-centred model. This had a great impact on the professor's role when deciding the relevant readings to be assigned before class and re-designing the experience during the class to achieve the learning objectives. On the other hand, students move from a passive role during the class to an anticipated active role before and even after the class time.

Another example, which demonstrates the need for clarifying the professor role, is the use of document sharing platforms in a PBL context: What is expected from the supervisor/facilitator: Should he or she simply give feedback to drafts and worksheets sent from the students to the supervisor, or is the supervisor equipped with access to the shared documents and expected to participate more actively and continuously in the writing process, now that he/she has access to both read, comment and edit directly in the documents?

We encourage faculty members to consider these roles when designing teaching and learning with the use of new technologies, and to make them explicit also to students and potential co-faculty members along with the goals presented in the previous section. This avoids students being confused or frustrated because they are unsure what they should do, what is expected from them and - eventually - how it can affect their gradings.

Table 2 suggests potential roles under the ACTIVE taxonomy highlighting that professors are transitioning towards facilitators of learner's processes and students are transitioning towards independent self-regulated learners. What is key in every field of the table is that both students and professors are aware of their roles, even when roles are changing compared to previous learning environments.

Table 2. Professor's and Student's roles regarding ACTIVE learning technologies

Taxonomy	Professor's Role	Student's Role
A	To design TLE that challenges students and triggers their critical thinking beyond these tools.	To identify and complement their knowledge gaps with the available tools while keeping a critical thinking relative to the findings.
C	To select the proper technology according to student's possibilities.	To suggest tools with which they are familiar or to train accordingly.
T	To design TLE that encourages students to share, discuss, and agree on teams.	To have a joint construction that is more powerful than the individual one.
I	To provide timely and meaningful feedback	To be participative in an objective and honest manner
V	To study their audience and highlight the importance of deeper comprehension beyond virtual environments.	To take the ownership for their learning, self-directing their process and self-regulating their pace.
E	To design formative, summative, graded and non-graded assessment opportunities.	To participate actively and critically against the level of learning achieved.

In particular, with respect to AI based technologies, we are questioning what new skills will be required in the AI era to support students in becoming metacognitive involved self-regulated learners (Ka Yuk Chan & Tsi, n.d.), since the same technology could serve different purposes. Also, we are questioning whether AI will replace the role of professors or will complement us in our process of guiding students on their learning journey.

5 Discussion

Nowadays, it is impossible to deny the high impact of technology in the TLE. However, more than ever we have to reflect not only on how to use it, but more importantly why to use it or why not. A wrong use of technology can discourage students and affect the metacognition process since the students will not understand the purpose of its use, or how to use it to better serve her or his learning process. This can lead not only to unhappy and frustrated students but can also discourage both the faculty involved and other faculty members in taking up and experimenting with new technologies. University environments can be conservative, and stories of failed experiments can confirm a reluctance of change among faculty members.

Currently, we as professors tend to use ICT tools during class to avoid bored students. However, its integration starts from the course design. Facilitators must define and explore which technologies really contribute to the expected goals, which technologies could be used during the class and which technologies could be useful at the closing or even after class. Some of the tools require planning in advance, the acquisition of software licences, or the use under certain constraints.

The Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) currently stand as fundamental allies or tools in educational processes. When employed appropriately within relevant contexts, ICT and AI act as facilitators in mediating between students, teachers, and the curriculum (Coll, 2004).

On one hand, interaction in digital environments, instant communication, and access to digital resources promote exploration and connection among diverse perspectives, innovative ideas, and challenging mechanisms of action. On the other hand, the digital recording of communications and learning processes offer valuable resources for fostering metacognitive reflection on the progress and challenges experienced during the learning process, as well as making pedagogical and didactic decisions based on data (Dai, Liu, & Lim, 2023).

Moreover, the integration of artificial intelligence into learning processes can become a strategic actor in stimulating thinking, as AI goes beyond technical functions and communicative mediations by including cognitive abilities such as pattern recognition, automation of thought processes, and analysis of convergences and divergences. This implies that AI can generate spaces for reflection on what has been learned, for collaborative creation, becoming an interlocutor of one's own thought through effective and creative human-AI communication (De Haro Olle, 2024).

Likewise, the integration of AI into the learning process favours the recognition of students' experiences, as personalised learning situations can be created to adapt to their needs and connect their previous experiences with the construction of new knowledge with meaning and significance.

By extending beyond the conventional classroom, these tools broaden spatial and temporal boundaries, which can improve interaction, collaboration, and more precise feedback. The appropriate use of ICT+AI resources can stimulate the design of enriched and flexible learning environments that adapt to the particular needs of each student, fostering interaction between teachers and students (Samoylenko et al., 2022).

Furthermore, it is important to consider that the incorporation of ICT and AI is also a way to value and recognize students' previous experiences with technology and their experiences in an increasingly digital and

interconnected world. To harness this potential, it is important to intentionally integrate ICT and AI into the planning of learning situations to identify, for example, the most relevant contexts for their application and make decisions that allow these technologies to act as enhancers of thinking, and never as replacements. It is necessary, therefore, to develop digital competencies that transcend their technical dimension towards a critical perspective of technological development that enables addressing the challenges posed by AI in aspects such as intellectual production, equity, discrimination, environmental impact, and collaboration with others (Universidad Icesi, 2023). In this regard, a pedagogical-technological approach is required that allows for critical, responsible, creative, and effective interaction with ICT + AI tools in learning, thinking, and experience processes.

ICT tools and the Generation of Teaching Practice Knowledge

ICT enables information to flow constantly between the interactions of a learning experience, and for this to occur, it is required that such information be made explicit.

For the proposed taxonomy dimension A, C and T are related to the creation of the learning environment. This process of transitioning from a teacher's tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge about what is taught and how it is taught allows for more rigorous planning and, in turn, enables more precise reflection on what happens in a classroom.

Specifically, this process of transitioning from tacit to explicit knowledge for teachers contributes to the creation of clearer instructions for students and the development of digital educational content. Furthermore, it contributes to the collective construction of knowledge derived from the implementation of a learning experience. Iliško et al. (2010) introduce the term 'teacher-researcher,' which 'characterises a reflective professional motivated to identify and address problems in their praxis' (p. 53). In this sense, the teacher is positioned at the center of knowledge production in the professional context of the classroom, with the purpose of: improving teaching practices, better understanding their actions, and thus, reclaiming their voice and making a difference (Iliško et al., 2010). In this way, the collective construction of such knowledge can range from personal and group reflective teaching practices to socialisation in academic events and the production of knowledge in education journals within the discipline.

ICT tools and the Learning Assessment Process

The assessment process in a learning active experience is embedded within it; that is to say, it is not an element added at the end, but rather an integral part of it from its conception, as assessment is understood as an experience for learning with others. For the proposed taxonomy, dimensions I, V and E are related to the assessment process.

In this sense, feedback is a fundamental piece, as it allows the student to progress not only in their cognitive and procedural knowledge but also in their sensitivity and human development. Specifically, timely and quality feedback that is used for student advancement in their process becomes necessary. Thus, the appropriate use of tools and technological resources stimulates the design of new flexible learning environments that adapt to the current needs of students and foster interaction between students and educators, thereby opening up new opportunities in the educational process (Samoylenko et al., 2022) by allowing the management of information flow in a learning experience, contributes to making such feedback information real-time, more precise, and explicit, thus creating contexts for the student to use it and also develop abilities for self-assessment and peer evaluation. Therefore, according to Miller & Staley (2021), timely feedback from both teachers and peers allows

the student to reflect on their educational process, giving meaning to their thoughts, emotions, and experiences in the learning process.

6 Conclusions

This paper discusses the intrinsic relationship between technology and active learning emphasizing the need of having clear goals and objectives about why to use it and how the TLE needs to be adapted to incorporate that technology. To facilitate this process, a taxonomy is presented in order to recognize the type of competencies the professor would like to develop. Likewise, the changes in the TLE environment and changes in student and professor's roles are detailed.

It is also important to consider that the taxonomy presented here is generic and that for each discipline, specific ICT and AI tools can provide meaningful experiences in each of the proposed dimensions. The taxonomy can be enriched, and it will continue evolving along with the rapid changes in technology but the main essence remains, the tool has to be aligned and it requires a purpose.

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